

Mood States (POMS) Condition Profile Analysis of Senior Women's Cricket Athletes in East Java before The North Aceh Sumatra PON 2024

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ABSTRACT: One factor that could affect an athlete's mental and emotional readiness is *mood*. Mood profile for *Cricket* athletes is an important factor that needs to be analyzed. An athlete's mood can affect their overall performance. A positive mood can increase focus, motivation, and self-confidence, while a negative mood can hinder an athlete's abilities and affect desired results. The aim of this research is to determine the condition of the Profile of Mood States (POMS) of East Java Female Senior *Cricket* Athletes before the 2024 Aceh North Sumatra PON. This research method uses descriptive quantitative research with seventeen athletes as the sample in the research and limited only to East Java Senior Female *Cricket* Athletes. The results of the research shows that the "Medium" category with the highest percentage is the anger indicator (AMR) at 72.27%, and the confused mood indicator (SSB) at 72.10%. Indicators with a medium percentage include indicators of full energy (PNT), self-assessment (PDR), and depression (DPS) of 70.59%. The percentage of fatigue indicators (KLH) was 69.08% and the indicator with the lowest category was the tension indicator (KTG) at 68.07%. The conclusion of the research on Profile of Mood States (POMS) Condition Analysis for East Java Women's Senior *Cricket* Athletes before the 2024 Aceh North Sumatra PON was in "Medium" condition. Negative mood conditions in the "Medium" category such as fatigue, anger, tension, confusion and depression indicate that athletes are not feeling stressed mentally and physically. Meanwhile, positive mood conditions in the "Medium" category make athletes have a good mood, such as being full of energy and self-confidence. This is possible because the training portion is good and the conditions for the 2024 Aceh North Sumatra PON are still quite long. So, there are still many athletes who experience good *mood* conditions.

KEYWORDS: *Cricket*, Female Athletes, Profile Of Mood States (POMS).

INTRODUCTION

Cricket is a team sport that has the aim of achieving achievements on the international stage and has several number of matches played on the international stage such as test matches, ODI (One Day International), IT20 (International Twenty 20) where the duration of the game can take one hour to two hours (Afandi & Susanto, 2017). Exercise is also often being done for a long time. Athletes often feel bored and fed up when training every day, this can increase the athlete's stress because they are tired, which results in the athlete being less enthusiastic and experiencing loss of motivation. Lack of trial practice against other clubs or other cricket teams and training for a long time is also a cause of burnout and boredom which can increase overtraining, resulting in stress and even injury (Almy & Aldapit, 2018). One factor that can influence an athlete's mental and emotional readiness is mood. Mood has many kinds of variations that change and can influence athletes to act, where a person's feelings can come at any time and anywhere with various duration and intensity (Melintika et al., 2017). Therefore, emotional instability or the athlete's mood will be the cause of stress and decreased mental health, which will affect other psychological functions and will ultimately have an impact on the athlete's performance.

Mood that has been measured in several countries includes tension, depression, anger, confusion, enthusiasm and fatigue. Apart from that, mood is said to be the most crucial factor in sports and can determine an athlete's success (Andrade et al., 2018). A person's good or bad mood can be influenced by the surrounding environment, such as when interacting with other individuals, uncomfortable environments, etc. With supportive environmental conditions, athletes will have good mood, just like when in a cricket team, each individual supports and encourages each other without bringing each other down, then the team will feel comfortable, happy, regain confidence, and have sense of trust in one another.

However, if an individual in the team has a bad mood, it will affect other individuals in the team, like restlessness, anger, anxiety, lack of self-confidence, and even loss of trust in each other (Melintika et al., 2017). Therefore, a bad mood condition can have a fatal impact on team performance, such as decision making when a competition is in progress. The mood condition of each individual

should be an important concern for a coach, where the coach must be able to know whether the athlete's mood condition is positive or negative. Inadvertently, this mood gives the athlete a good or bad performance, so that when the athlete is in a bad mood it can be dangerous for the athlete, for example the athlete can get tired quickly and suffer an injury. In fact, the risk of injury can also occur due to excessive load and poor quality of rest or sleep (Wahyudi & Fajarwati, 2020).

Thus, the problem that researchers can find is that when the athlete is in a good mood, the athlete can carry out all the training programs that day well and in accordance with the target of achieving training results. An athlete's mood can affect their overall performance. A positive mood can increase focus, motivation and self-confidence, while a negative mood can hinder an athlete's abilities and affect desired results. Mood states or mood when athletes are performing training include fatigue, angry mood, feeling ready, energetic, full of energy, tension, self-assessment, confused, and depression (Gultom, 2018). Even though mood is an important factor in the mental and emotional readiness of cricket athletes, not much research has been conducted to analyze the mood profile of cricket athletes in East Java.

METHOD

This research uses a type of quantitative research using a descriptive approach. This research was carried out at the training ground for East Java Cricket athletes, namely the UNESA East Java Softball field. In accordance with the aim of the research, namely to determine the condition of the Profile of Mood States (POMS) of East Java Female Senior Cricket Athletes, the sampling technique used was purposive sampling. The sample for this research consisted of seventeen athletes consisting of senior female cricket athletes from East Java who would compete in PON, where the entire population of senior female cricket athletes from East Java was used as the research sample. Therefore, this research is included in total sampling research. The research was conducted for one month, where athletes were asked to fill out the Profile Of Mood States (POMS) questionnaire with a rating scale. The POMS questionnaire used is the Indonesian version (Wahyudi & Fajarwati, 2020) which consists of thirty-five statement items with seven indicators. Data collection was carried out by adding up all scores per indicator and analyzed using statistical analysis techniques. This research method uses descriptive percentage analysis with the formula ;

$$P = \frac{f}{N} \times 100\%$$

Information :

P: Percentage

f : Answer Frequency

N: Number of Respondents' Answers

After processing the data using this formula, continue using the category formula or formulation, namely;

Table.1 Categories (Muslim et al., 2022)

intervals	Categories
M+1,5SD<X	Very High
M+0,5SD<X≤M+1,5SD	High
M-0,5SD<X≤M+0,5SD	Medium
M-1,5SD<X≤M-0,5SD	Low
X≤M-1,5SD	Very Low

Information :

M: Mean

SD: Standard Deviation

X : Score (%)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

I. RESULTS

As a result of the questionnaire that was filled out by seventeen East Java senior female cricket athletes who filled out the POMS questionnaire, the percentage of each indicator is known as follows;

1. Fatigue Indicator (KLH)

Table 2. Percentage of Fatigue Indicators (KLH)

Sub-Indicators	KLH. 1	KLH. 8	KLH. 15	KLH. 22	KLH. 29
f	83	83	73	87	85
N	119	119	119	119	119
f/N	0,6975	0,6975	0,6134	0,7311	0,7143
P(%)	69,75%	69,75%	61,34%	73,11%	71,43%
Mean	69,08%				
Kategori	S	S	R	T	S

Based on the results of research data analysis conducted on East Java female senior circuit athletes who will take part in PON 2024. . A total of 17 respondents had a level of fatigue (KLH) obtained by the lowest (minimum) score of 61.34%, the highest score (maximum) 73.11%, the average (mean) 69.08%, so it was obtained that the athlete's level of fatigue (KLH) The East Java women's senior circuit who will take part in PON 2024, is in the "Medium" category with a total of 69.08%.

2. Anger Indicator (AMR)

Table 3. Percentage of Anger Indicators (AMR)

Sub-Indicators	AMR. 2	AMR. 9	AMR. 16	AMR. 23	AMR. 30
f	90	89	82	84	85
N	119	119	119	119	119
f/N	0,7563	0,7479	0,6891	0,7059	0,7143
P(%)	75,63%	74,79%	68,91%	70,59%	71,43%
Mean	72,27%				
Kategori	T	T	R	R	S

Based on the results of research data analysis conducted on East Java female senior circuit athletes who will take part in PON 2024. A total of 17 respondents had an anger level (AMR), the lowest (minimum) score was 68.91%, the highest (maximum) score was 75.63%, the average (mean) is 72.27%, so it is found that the anger level (AMR) of East Java female senior circuit athletes who will take part in PON 2024, is in the "Medium" category with a total of 72.27%.

3. Full Power Indicator (PNT)

Table 4. Percentage of Full Power Indicator (PNT)

Sub-Indicators	PNT.3	PNT.10	PNT.17	PNT.24	PNT.31
f	87	72	84	84	93
N	119	119	119	119	119
f/N	0,7311	0,6050	0,7059	0,7059	0,7815
P(%)	73,11%	60,50%	70,59%	70,59%	78,15%
Mean	70,59%				
Kategori	T	SR	S	S	T

Based on the results of research data analysis conducted on East Java female senior circuit athletes who will take part in PON 2024. A total of 17 respondents who had a full power level (PNT) obtained the lowest (minimum) score of 60.50%, the highest (maximum) score of 78.15% , the average (mean) is 70.59%, so it is found that the full energy level (PNT) of East Java female senior circuit athletes who will take part in PON 2024, is in the "Medium" category with a total of 70.59%.

4. Tension Indicator (KTG)

Table 5. Percentage of Tension Indicators (KTG)

Sub-Indicators	KTG.4	KTG.11	KTG.18	KTG.25	KTG. 32
f	76	80	92	82	75
N	119	119	119	119	119
f/N	0,6387	0,6723	0,7731	0,6891	0,6303
P(%)	63,87%	67,23%	77,31%	68,91%	63,03%
Mean	68,07%				
Kategori	R	S	ST	S	R

Based on the results of research data analysis conducted on East Java female senior circuit athletes who will take part in PON 2024. A total of 17 respondents had a level of tension (KTG) obtained the lowest score (minimum) 63.03%, the highest score (maximum) 77.31%, the average (mean) is 68.07%, so it is found that the tension level (KTG) of East Java female senior circuit athletes who will take part in PON 2024, is in the "Medium" category with a total of 68.07%.

5. Self Assessment Indicators (PDR)

Table 6. Percentage of Self Assessment Indicators (PDR)

Sub-Indicators	PDR. 5	PDR.12	PDR.19	PDR.26	PDR.33
f	85	88	76	82	89
N	119	119	119	119	119
f/N	0,7143	0,7395	0,6387	0,6891	0,7479
P(%)	71,43%	73,95%	63,87%	68,91%	74,79%
Mean	70,59%				
Kategori	S	T	SR	S	T

Based on the results of research data analysis conducted on East Java female senior circuit athletes who will take part in PON 2024. A total of 17 respondents had a level of tension (KTG) obtained the lowest (minimum) score of 63.87%, the highest (maximum) score of 74.79%, the average (mean) is 70.59%, so it is found that the self-assessment level (PDR) of East Java female senior circuit athletes who will take part in PON 2024, is in the "Medium" category with a total of 70.59%.

6. Confused Mood Indicator (SSB)

Table 7. Percentage of Confused Mood Indicators (SSB)

Sub-Indicators	SSB.6	SSB.13	SSB.20	SSB.27	SSB.34
F	83	81	90	91	84
N	119	119	119	119	119
f/N	0,6975	0,6807	0,7563	0,7647	0,7059
P(%)	69,75%	68,07%	75,63%	76,47%	70,59%
Mean	72,10%				
Kategori	R	R	T	T	S

Based on the results of research data analysis conducted on East Java female senior circuit athletes who will take part in PON 2024. A total of 17 respondents had a level of confused mood (SSB), the lowest (minimum) score was 68.07%, the highest (maximum) score was 76.47% , the average (mean) is 72.10%, so it is found that the self-assessment level (PDR) of East Java female senior circuit athletes who will take part in PON 2024, is in the "Medium" category with a total of 72.10%.

7. Depression Indicator (DPR)

Table 8. Percentage of Depression Indicators (DPR)

Sub-Indicators	DPS.	DPS.	DPS.	DPS.	DPS.
F	7	14	21	28	35
N	78	91	77	84	90
F/N	119	119	119	119	119
P(%)	0,6555	0,7647	0,6471	0,7059	0,7563
Mean	65,55%	76,47%	64,71%	70,59%	75,63%
Kategori	70,59%				
	S	T	R	S	T

Based on the results of research data analysis conducted on East Java female senior circuit athletes who will take part in PON 2024. A total of 17 respondents had a level of depression (DPS) with the lowest (minimum) score of 63.87%, the highest (maximum) score of 74.79%, the average (mean) is 70.59%, so it is found that the level of depression (DPS) of East Java female senior circuit athletes who will take part in PON 2024, is in the "Medium" category with a total of 70.59%.

II. DISCUSSION

The results of the analysis of questionnaire data from each indicator, namely the fatigue indicator (KLH) in the "Medium" category, where the average athlete's condition is fatigue, such as even though they have rested, their body is still tired, they feel weak, they lack energy, their muscles ache even though they have rested for a long time, they feel helpless. carrying out tasks, and throughout the day the body feels unfit. Therefore, recovery is very important for an athlete who experiences fatigue every day like this so that it does not affect the quality of their movements (Gultom, 2018). In this condition, East Java Women's Senior Cricket athletes before the 2024 Aceh North Sumatra PON still do not feel tired, such as a sluggish body, sore muscles, helplessness and not being fit.

The anger indicator (AMR) is in the "Medium" category, however, almost all athletes experience this condition, especially in the AMR.2 sub-indicator which states "I feel disappointed" in other words, this disappointment is the highest among other sub-indicators such as remembering disappointing events, I find it difficult to control my emotions when I'm upset, I feel tense, and I find it difficult to control my anger. This indicator has an important role in building athletes' competitive spirit. Anger (AMR) can also increase emotions, but this emotional condition must be suppressed and controlled so that it becomes a positive emotion so that it will become energy that can motivate athletes to increase their enthusiasm and high fighting power during training and competitions (Gultom, 2018). The "Medium" category indicates that the athlete does not feel disappointed, is able to control emotions, is tense and holds back anger.

Sub-indicators of the full energy indicator (PNT), namely; I feel overloaded with energy, all tasks feel light, I can do tasks for hours, I feel steady, full of energy, and I feel confident. Of all these indicators, the average obtained was 70.59%, which indicates that East Java female cricket athletes have the energy that can be said to be ready to carry out training activities. The conditions that occurred in the East Java Senior Female Cricket Athletes before the 2024 Aceh North Sumatra PON were said to be "Medium" but in theory it could be said to be "Good". Where the athlete's current mood is still in a condition where he is able to do the task, is confident, full of energy, does not feel like he is being overburdened and is able to do the task.

In the Tension Indicator (KTG) with the "Medium" category, they feel tense during training, this is due to a lack of experience competing and training with more intensity than each athlete's portion. Apart from that, stress can also affect

athletes' psychological conditions, such as anxiety, self-confidence and concentration. This can have an impact on athletes' performance in competitions (Pradipta, 2007). Therefore, it is important to manage stress and tension effectively so that it does not hinder an athlete's performance. Several stress management techniques, such as relaxation exercises and tension management, can help athletes overcome the negative impact of tension and stress on their physical and psychological condition (Mutmainnah & Kasmad, 2022). This indicates that athletes do not feel too much anxiety or tension in facing PON 2024.

The self-assessment indicator (PDR) for East Java female senior cricket athletes is categorized as "Medium" which means that if the athlete still lacks confidence in carrying out their duties, a lack of confidence arises which can affect the quality of their training. If athletes have high self-confidence then they can strengthen the team because with self-confidence they can emit positive emotions which have a big influence on the surrounding environment. With athletes who are confident, they can be calmer and concentrate better when training so they don't get tense when competing or doing extra routine training (Wahyudi & Fajarwati, 2020). This category indicates that the athlete has a sufficient level of self-confidence and is able to carry out the task well.

In the confused atmosphere indicator (SSB) there are five sub-indicators, namely feeling stuck in the mind, unable to concentrate, confused thoughts because of too much information, making decisions that are awry, and having difficulty forgetting failures which are categorized as "Medium". A confused atmosphere can occur when an athlete does not easily take in information from the environment, which can worsen the condition of the team and the athlete himself. Because the indicator of a confused atmosphere itself is a negative psychological condition. This category indicates that the athlete feels they can concentrate well and do not feel confused by the directions given by the coach, manager and captain.

East Java Women's Cricket athletes experience "Moderate" depressed mood (DPS) because they do high intensity training which can last six days in a row and many athletes stay up late at night. The conditions that occurred in the East Java Senior Female Cricket Athletes before the 2024 Aceh North Sumatra PON were said to be "Medium" but in theory it could be said to be "Good". In this condition, East Java senior female cricket athletes do not experience reduced appetite, difficulty sleeping, and do not feel ostracized.

From the description above, it can be seen that the Profile of Mood States condition of East Java Women's Cricket athletes is in "Medium" condition. Thus, East Java senior female cricket athletes do not feel mentally and physically stressed, such as fatigue, anger, full of energy, tension, self-judgment, confusion and depression. This is possible because the training portion is good and the conditions leading up to PON Aceh, North Sumatra 2024 are still quite long. So there are still many athletes who experience good mood conditions.

CONCLUSION

From the description of the discussion above, it can be concluded that the Profile of Mood States condition of East Java Women's Cricket athletes is in "Medium" condition. Where the negative mood condition is categorized as "Medium" which indicates that the athlete is not feeling mentally and physically stressed, such as fatigue, anger, tension, confusion and depression. For positive mood conditions, it is categorized as "Medium", where this condition makes the talent have a good mood or mood, such as being full of energy and confident. This is possible because the training portion is good and the conditions leading up to PON Aceh, North Sumatra 2024 are still quite long. So there are still many athletes who experience good mood conditions.

RECOMMENDATION

This questionnaire model can also be used for other sports.

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